

Cervical Cancer Knowledge and Awareness Among Females of Varying Ages in Multan

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Abstract

Cervical cancer is a leading cause of death among women worldwide, with an estimated 570,000 new cases and 311,000 deaths annually. To assess the level of awareness and understanding of cervical cancer and its prevention among women in Multan, Pakistan, a nine-month survey was conducted with 825 participants from CHM and Nishtar Hospital Multan. The questionnaire used in this study was divided into three sections: socio-demographic information, knowledge and awareness of cervical cancer, and awareness of cervical cancer prevention and vaccination. Based on the results, all three groups had a relatively low level of knowledge about cervical cancer, its symptoms, risk factors, and screening methods. Group 1 had the lowest level of knowledge in all three categories, indicating a significant need for awareness and education. Group 3 had a better level of knowledge compared to Group 1 but still had a low level of knowledge about cervical cancer symptoms and the Pap test. It is essential to prioritize awareness and education programs to improve knowledge and promote prevention measures, such as Pap tests and HPV vaccination, to reduce the incidence and mortality of cervical cancer in Multan and Pakistan as a whole. Further research with larger sample sizes and more hospitals is recommended to improve the generalizability of the findings.

Keywords: cervical cancer, Human papillomavirus, pap test, screening, vaccination

Introduction

Cervical cancer initiates in the cervix, the lower part of the uterus connecting to the vagina. It is a prevalent form of cancer in women globally, with approximately 570,000 new cases and 311,000 fatalities reported every year (1). Cervical cancer is primarily caused by the human papillomavirus (HPV), which is a sexually transmitted infection.. Other factors that elevate the likelihood of cervical cancer include smoking, a compromised immune system, and a familial history of the disease. Cervical cancer

may not present any symptoms in its early stages, which is why regular screening is essential for early detection and treatment.

The fourth most frequent type of cancer affecting women globally, as stated by the World Health Organization (WHO), is cervical cancer. An estimated 570,000 new cases of cervical cancer were diagnosed worldwide in 2018, accounting for 6.6% of all female cancers (2). Sub-Saharan Africa has the most notable occurrence rates of cervical cancer, trailed by South Asia, Latin America, and the Caribbean. In 2018, cervical cancer was responsible for an estimated 311,000 deaths worldwide, accounting for 7.5% of all female cancer deaths (3). Cervical cancer mortality rates are highest in sub-Saharan Africa and lower in developed countries where screening programs and HPV vaccination are more prevalent. Limited access to cervical cancer screening and treatment in low and middle-income countries results in a majority of cervical cancer cases being detected at advanced stages, leading to higher mortality rates (4). These statistics underscore the importance of effective cervical cancer prevention and screening programs, as well as access to timely and appropriate treatment, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Cervical cancer is a significant public health issue in Pakistan, with high incidence and mortality rates. According to the Globocan 2020 database, there were an estimated 10,000 new cases of cervical cancer and 10,070 5-year prevalence (all ages) deaths due to the disease in Pakistan in 2020 (5). The incidence of cervical cancer in Pakistan is among the highest in the world, with a rate of 9.6 cases per 100,000 women. Cervical cancer is the second most common cancer among women in Pakistan, after breast cancer. The elevated occurrence and fatality rates of cervical cancer in Pakistan can be attributed to multiple factors (6). Limited access to healthcare and cervical cancer screening programs, low levels of awareness about the disease and its risk factors, and social and cultural factors that may discourage women from seeking care are among the main barriers to prevention and treatment. The objective of this study was to assess the current level of awareness among females in Multan, Pakistan, regarding cervical cancer.

Methodology:

In Multan, Pakistan, a survey was conducted to assess women's knowledge and comprehension of cervical cancer and its prevention measures. The study, which took place for nine months, involved 825 participants from CHM and Nishtar Hospital Multan. This is the first research of its kind to be conducted in Multan, and the questionnaire was created by referring to previous research and literature on the subject. The questionnaire had three main sections, which included socio-demographic information, knowledge and awareness of cervical cancer, and awareness of cervical cancer prevention and vaccination. The data was analyzed with proportions and percentages computed for all variables. The relationship between nominal variables was evaluated on basis of percentage values.

Results and Discussion:

The patients' ages ranged from 18 to 70 years old. Most of the female patients (50.3%) were between 40 and 70 years old. Out of the 825 female patients, 70% belonged to a low socioeconomic status, and only 30% had received an education. Additionally, 80% of the respondents had husbands who were employed in manual labor jobs such as rickshaw drivers, laborers, and peddlers. 10% of the females reported that their husbands were unemployed, while the remaining 10% had well-established employment status.

Table 1: Characteristics of participants.

	Age	
	Frequency n=825	Percentage %
18-20	180	22
21-45	230	28
46-70	415	50
	Marital status	
Married	200	24
Unmarried	425	52
Other	200	24

Table 1 portrays the features of the individuals involved in the study, where 825 individuals were included. The majority of the participants (50%) were aged between 46 to 70 years old. Regarding marital status, 52% of the participants were unmarried.

Table 2: Information about symptoms of Cervical Cancer

Age Groups	Yes %	No %
Group 1	28	72
Group 2	65	35
Group 3	60	40

Table 2 provides information on the symptoms of cervical cancer across three age groups. Among Group 1 participants, 28% reported experiencing symptoms associated with cervical cancer, while 72% did not. In Group 2, 65% reported experiencing symptoms, and 35% did not. In Group 3, 60% reported experiencing symptoms, and 40% did not. Based on these percentages, we can see that Group 2 has the highest percentage of people who answered "Yes" (65%), indicating that this group has the highest level of knowledge about the symptoms of cervical cancer. Group 3 follows with 60%, and Group 1 has the lowest percentage of people who answered "Yes" (28%). Therefore, we can conclude that Group 2 has the most information about the symptoms of cervical cancer, while Group 1 has the least information.

Table 3: Information about risk factor Cervical Cancer

Age Groups	Yes %	No %
Group 1	22	78
Group 2	78	22
Group 3	36	64

Table 3 presents data on the cervical cancer risk factors across the three age categories. In Group 1, 22% reported having risk factors associated with cervical cancer, while 78% did not. In Group 2, 78% reported having risk factors, and 22% did not. In Group 3, 36% reported having risk factors, while 64% did not. Based on these percentages, we can see that Group 2 has the highest percentage of people who answered "Yes" (78%), indicating that this group has the highest level of knowledge about the factors that increase the likelihood of developing cervical cancer. Group 3 follows with 36%, and Group 1 has the lowest percentage of people who answered "Yes" (22%). Therefore, we can conclude that Group 2 has the most information about the risk factors for cervical cancer, while Group 1 has the least information.

Table 4: Ever heard about pap test?

Age Groups	Yes %	No %
Group 1	17	83
Group 2	26	74
Group 3	19	81

Table 4 reports on the participants' knowledge about the pap test across the three age groups. In Group 1, only 17% of the participants had heard about the pap test, while 83% had not. Within Group 2, 26% were aware of the pap test, whereas 74% were not. In Group 3, 19% had knowledge about the pap test, while 81% did not.. Based on these percentages, we can see that all three groups have a relatively low level of knowledge about the Pap test, with only a small percentage of people in each group having ever heard about it. Among the three groups, Group 2 has the highest percentage of people who have heard about the Pap test (26%), followed by Group 3 (19%) and Group 1 (17%). Therefore, we can conclude that overall, these three groups have a low level of knowledge about the Pap test, with Group 2 having slightly more knowledge than the other two groups.

According to a study conducted among females in Punjab, Pakistan, the level of knowledge was found to be poor. Nevertheless, there was a favorable outlook noted concerning programs related to cervical cancer awareness. The investigation unveiled a significant dearth of information among participants about the risk elements linked to cervical cancer and the cervical cancer vaccine's accessibility. Nearly all of the respondents (99%) exhibited inadequate knowledge on this subject. Additionally, the research identified a noteworthy correlation between the degree of education and the knowledge of cervical cancer, its method of transmission, and screening exams (7). Similarly, In the study conducted in Karachi, Pakistan, the participants' age was 30 (± 7.6) years on average. Out of the women who were surveyed, 61.2% were familiar with cervical cancer, and among them, only 47.0% knew about the Pap smear test, with 73% of them having undergone the test. A meager 25.5% of the women surveyed knew about the existence of a vaccine for the cervical cancer prevention, and out of those, only 9.8% had received the human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine (8). It is not possible to make a direct comparison between the level of awareness and knowledge in Multan, Lahore and Karachi, Pakistan. Each study has its own unique sample size,

demographics, and methodology, which could impact the results. Therefore, it is important to consider each study's findings independently and evaluate the need for awareness and education in each population separately.

Based on the results, Group 1 appears to have the lowest level of knowledge across all three categories - symptoms, risk factors, and awareness about the Pap test. Therefore, it can be concluded that Group 1 needs awareness the most. Nevertheless, it's crucial to acknowledge that the three groups possess a comparatively insufficient level of understanding, emphasizing the need for awareness, recognition, or knowledge about cervical cancer, its symptoms, risk factors, and screening procedures.

Group 3 has a relatively better level of knowledge compared to Group 1, but still has a low level of knowledge about the symptoms of cervical cancer and the Pap test. However, Group 3 has a significantly lower level of knowledge about the risk factors for cervical cancer compared to Group 2. Therefore, while Group 3 may not need awareness as much as Group 1, there is still a need for education and awareness about cervical cancer in this group, particularly regarding risk factors.

Further research is recommended to collect data from more hospitals and a larger sample size to gain a more comprehensive understanding of cervical cancer awareness and education among females in Multan. However, based on the current study's findings, it can be concluded that there is a significant need for cervical cancer awareness and education in the region. The inadequate understanding of cervical cancer symptoms, risk factors, and screening methods among the three groups highlights the significance of giving priority to awareness and educational initiatives. Encouraging preventive measures, such as Pap tests and HPV vaccination, is essential to reduce the prevalence and mortality of cervical cancer in Multan and throughout Pakistan.

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